

Haemolymph extraction from mantis shrimp (*Oratosquilla oratoria*) and mud crab (*Scylla serrata*) and its antimicrobial activity against *Staphylococcus epidermidis* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*: A comparative study

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Abstract

In an aquatic environment where microorganisms are abundant, crustaceans that have lived here have developed an effective system for detecting and eliminating noxious microorganisms. The haemolymph serves as the fluid that circulates in the body of marine invertebrates, where nutrients, oxygen, hormones and cells are located. These fluids also have a biological process that may be similar to vertebrate antibodies, which may help activate their innate immune mechanisms and help to fight or clean pathogens that may infect them. This research aims to determine and compare the antimicrobial property of haemolymph extract from mantis shrimp (*Oratosquilla oratoria*) and mud crab (*Scylla serrata*) against *Staphylococcus epidermidis* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. To begin with, mantis shrimps and crabs were collected from a local market in Cavite City, Cavite. For the extraction, the researchers collected the haemolymph of mantis shrimp (*Oratosquilla oratoria*) by suction from the pericardial sinus using sterile syringe and haemolymph from mud crab (*Scylla serrata*) was collected by cutting each walking leg of the animal with fine sterile scissors. The haemolymph was mixed with an anticoagulant solution [sodium citrate buffer, pH 4.6 (2:1, V/V)] to avoid degranulation and coagulation of the extract. Then, the samples were subjected to centrifugation at 10,000 RPM for 10 minutes at 4°C to remove haemocytes from plasma, then supernatant was aspirated and stored at 4°C until use. The antimicrobial activity of haemolymph from mantis shrimp and mud crab was assayed against *Staphylococcus epidermidis* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* using 10µl, 20µl, 30µl, and 40µl of the extract. Agar well diffusion method was used as the susceptibility method for testing the test organisms of interest.

Keywords: Haemolymph; Extraction; Mantis shrimp (*Oratosquilla oratoria*); Mud crab (*Scylla serrata*); Antimicrobial activity; *Staphylococcus epidermidis*; *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

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Introduction

Antibiotics are the front-line cure for bacterial infections. They are drugs that terminate or slow down the progress of bacteria, and therefore, play a significant role in modern medicine. However, bacteria are becoming resistant to a wide range of antibiotics, as a consequence of natural processes and widespread anthropogenic activity, resulting in causing a vast concern. The misuse and abuse of antibiotics leads to the development of multidrug resistant strains and might as well result to ineffective synthetic medicines.

Oceans are considered to be the habitat of an incredible collection of wild species, from tiny plankton to huge creatures that have ever existed. An aquatic habitat contains plenty of microorganisms, and because of this, creatures that live here are vulnerable to acquiring infectious diseases. Therefore, marine species developed an efficient system for recognizing and terminating harmful pathogens.

Crustaceans form a very large group of arthropods, and are usually considered as a subphylum, which includes familiar animals such as crabs, lobsters, crayfish, shrimp, krill and barnacles (Ganga.G, 2016). Their defense mechanism against microbes depends hugely on cellular activities performed by haemocytes such as adhesion, phagocytosis, encapsulation, nodule formation, and myelination (Haug et al., 2002; Prakash et al., 2011). All living organisms, including bacteria, plants, invertebrates and vertebrates, depend also on their antimicrobial peptides as their defense molecules. It seems that the sources of antibiotics came from organisms and the quest for new constituents of antibiotics can also be found in different species.

The progression of antibiotic-resistant infectious bacteria has triggered the search for alternative antimicrobial agents from natural sources. The emergence of new infectious diseases and resistance to the antibiotics by the existing ones which were synthetic, led to the need of new sources for drug discovery (Priya et al., 2014).

Crustaceans possess an open circulatory system, where nutrients, oxygen, hormones, and cells are distributed in the haemolymph (Fredrick & Ravichandran, 2012). In most of the crustacean species studied, the antimicrobial activity was located in the haemolymph and/or in the haemocytes. Haemolymph is a fluid in the circulatory system of some arthropods; they help to discard waste materials, carry nutrients, and clean the system of pathogens and debris. Studies on the immunity of invertebrates have focused on identifying defense mechanisms and biochemical pathways activated during an infection, and on identifying cell-free haemolymph and cellular factors involved in the destruction of pathogens, regulation, and damage repair (Vazquez et al., 2009).

Mantis shrimps belong to the group of marine crustaceans and also possess haemolymph. There are around 400 species of mantis shrimps that inhabit shallow subtropical and tropical waters of the Indian and Pacific Oceans. Mantis shrimps are only about four inches long, but pound for pound, are one of the strongest animals in the world. They are significant as commercial species in Japan and are commonly eaten as Shako (Antony et al., 2010).

Crabs are a type of marine crustacean related to prawns, shrimps, and lobster. They also possess haemolymph and have the presence of thick armoured shells which protect them from immediate danger. More than 6,700 known species are found in oceans worldwide, commonly in shallower ocean water where they tend to inhabit rocky pools and coral reefs, crabs are commercially eaten worldwide (Agbayani, 2001).

Staphylococcus epidermidis nowadays, is recognized as a significant opportunistic pathogen. It is currently the most frequent cause of nosocomial infections and represents the most common source of contaminations on indwelling medical devices. Among the Coagulase Negative *Staphylococcus* species, *S. epidermidis* clearly causes the greatest number of infections, and it is very likely to contaminate patient-care apparatus and environmental surfaces, perhaps clarifying the high frequency of *S. epidermidis* in the hospital setting (Otto, 2009).

Pseudomonas aeruginosa infection is commonly associated with nosocomial infections, often severe and fatal, particularly in immunocompromised hosts. *P. aeruginosa* is a common cause of hospital-acquired urinary tract infections, often associated with an indwelling catheter, and also the most significant pathogen in cystic fibrosis. Its main habitat is soil, but it can also be found in freshwater environments, as well as sinks, showers, respiratory apparatus, even contaminated distilled water. *P. aeruginosa* is categorized as an opportunistic pathogen. It is also inherently resistant to various classes of antimicrobial agents and can obtain additional resistance genes from other organisms (Wisplinghoff et al., 2018).

Per the knowledge that has been discussed above, it may be concluded that microorganisms are becoming resistant to the current antibiotics in this generation, due to the use of incorrect medications in self-medication. Therefore, the search for new antimicrobial compounds is needed. Thus, the crustaceans which contain haemolymph might be the key to the exploration of fresh antimicrobial compounds and may be an alternative source in the reduction efficiency of the current antibiotics (Mahon & Lehman, 2019).

Statement of the Problem

This study compared the antimicrobial activity of mantis shrimp (*Oratosquilla oratoria*) and mud crab (*Scylla serrata*) haemolymph extract against *Staphylococcus epidermidis* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Scientifically, this study answered the following questions:

1. How can the mantis shrimp (*Oratosquilla oratoria*) and mud crab (*Scylla serrata*) haemolymph be extracted?
2. What is the antimicrobial activity of mantis shrimp (*Oratosquilla oratoria*) and mud crab (*Scylla serrata*) haemolymph extract in the following volumes?

- 2.1. 10 µl (v/v) mantis shrimp and mud crab haemolymph extract
- 2.2. 20 µl (v/v) mantis shrimp and mud crab haemolymph extract
- 2.3. 30 µl (v/v) mantis shrimp and mud crab haemolymph extract
- 2.4. 40 µl (v/v) mantis shrimp and mud crab haemolymph extract
3. Is there any significant difference in the antimicrobial activity of mantis shrimp (*Oratosquilla oratoria*) and mud crab (*Scylla serrata*) haemolymph extract with various volumes and control? Does the mantis shrimp (*Oratosquilla oratoria*) haemolymph extract exhibit more antimicrobial activity than the mud crab (*Scylla serrata*) against *Staphylococcus epidermidis* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*?

Research Methodology

The experimental method was used in this study to determine the antibacterial effect of mantis shrimp (*Oratosquilla oratoria*) and mud crab (*Scylla serrata*) haemolymph extract. The procedure started after the collection of the sample. The researchers used suction by sterile syringe to obtain the haemolymph from the mantis shrimp and for the collection of haemolymphs in crab, fine sterile scissors were used. An anticoagulant buffer was added to prevent denaturation and clotting of the sample.

A plastic container was used for the proper transport of the sample. During the extraction procedure, sterile syringes were used for the collection of haemolymph. The refrigerated centrifuge was used to separate haemocytes from the plasma, and then the supernatant was removed and stored until use.

The mantis shrimp and mud crab that were used in the study were collected and purchased from the public market in Cavite City, Cavite. The mantis shrimp and mud crab that were used in the study was verified in the University of the Philippines, Museum of Natural History, Los Baños, Laguna.

About 0.5 mL of haemolymph was extracted from the mantis shrimp by the use of sterile syringe by suction from the pericardial sinus through the articular membrane between the fourth and fifth tergite (Ferrero et al., 1983). For the haemolymph of the crab, 3 mL of haemolymph was collected by cutting each walking leg of the mud crab with fine sterile scissors (Hajirasouli et al. 2014). Then the extract was placed in sodium citrate-buffer pH 4.6 (2:1, V/V) to avoid degranulation and coagulation. An equal volume of physiological saline (0.85% NaCl, W/V) was also added to it. To remove haemocytes from plasma, haemolymph was centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 10 minutes at 4°C and the supernatant was aspirated and stored at 4°C until use (Sumalatha et al. 2018), with modifications.

The test organisms *Staphylococcus epidermidis* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* were purchased at the Pasig City Children's Hospital. The test organisms (*Staphylococcus epidermidis* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*) were adjusted to a final density of 105 CFU/mL by diluting fresh cultures and by comparing with McFarland density and Wickerham card.

Antimicrobial activity of haemolymph extract was evaluated by agar well diffusion method. In a Mueller Hinton Agar, colonies from the inoculum were streaked and a cork borer (6 mm diameter) was used to punch wells in solidified medium and was loaded with different quantities of haemolymph such as 10µl, 20µl, 30µl, and 40µl.

Gentamicin was used as a positive control and Dimethylsulfoxide as a negative control for *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The plates were incubated at 37°C overnight and the zones of inhibition around the well were measured by vernier caliper (Singh et al., 2007) with modifications.

The statistical method that was used to compare the efficiency of the haemolymph extract of mantis shrimp (*Oratosquilla oratoria*) and mud crab (*Scylla serrata*) against *Staphylococcus epidermidis* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). This allowed the researchers to further identify the comparable amount of antimicrobial activity of haemolymph extract from mantis shrimp (*Oratosquilla oratoria*) and mud crab (*Scylla serrata*) versus the positive and negative controls.

Results and Discussion

1. How does the mantis shrimp (*Oratosquilla oratoria*) and mud crab (*Scylla serrata*) haemolymph be extracted?

Two and a half (2 ½) kilos of mantis shrimp (*Oratosquilla oratoria*) and nine pieces of crab (*Scylla serrata*) were collected in a public market in Cavite City, Cavite, Philippines. 0.5 milliliters of extracted mantis shrimp haemolymph were placed in five milliliters (0.5) red tubes with sodium citrate-buffer having a pH of 4.6 (2:1, V/V). Three milliliters (3 mL) of extracted crab haemolymph was also placed in five milliliters (5 mL) red tubes with sodium citrate- buffer, having a pH of 4.6 (2:1, V/V). An equal volume of physiological saline (0.85% NaCl, W/V) was also added. The mixtures were centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 10 minutes at 4°C and the supernatant is aspirated and stored at 4°C until use.

2. What is the antimicrobial activity of mantis shrimp (*Oratosquilla oratoria*) and mud crab (*Scylla serrata*) haemolymph extract in the following volumes?

- 2.1. 10 µl (v/v) mantis shrimp and crab haemolymph extract
- 2.2. 20 µl (v/v) mantis shrimp and crab haemolymph extract
- 2.3. 30 µl (v/v) mantis shrimp and crab haemolymph extract
- 2.4. 40 µl (v/v) mantis shrimp and crab haemolymph extract

Table 1. Size of inhibition between mantis shrimp (*Oratosquilla oratoria*) and mud crab (*Scylla serrata*) haemolymphs at different concentration volume for *Staphylococcus epidermidis* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*

Bacteria	Volume (uL)	Mantis Size	Crab Size (mm)
<i>S. epidermidis</i>	10	7.67	7.67
	20	10.33	8.67
	30	13.00	10.33
	40	15.33	13.33
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	10	7.00	6.67
	20	8.67	8.67
	30	11.67	10.67
	40	13.67	13.33

It can be garnered from Table 1 that the extracted haemolymphs of mantis shrimp exhibit antibacterial effects against *Staphylococcus epidermidis* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* at 10 uL (7.67, 7.00), 20uL (10.33, 8.67), 30uL (13.00, 11.67), and 40 uL (15.33, 13.67). On the other hand, the extracted haemolymphs of crab also exhibit antibacterial effects against *Staphylococcus epidermidis* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* at 10 uL (7.67, 6.67), 20 uL (8.67, 8.67), 30 uL (10.33, 10.67) and 40 uL (13.33, 13.33). These results are interpreted as an intermediate antibacterial effect. Despite the fact that the haemolymph exhibits antimicrobial activity, they are still not comparable to the positive control in treating *Staphylococcus epidermidis* (24, 21, and 22) and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (18, 17, and 18). At the same time, the negative control did not exhibit antimicrobial property to both organisms.

3. Is there any significant difference in the antimicrobial activity of mantis shrimp (*Oratosquilla oratoria*) and mud crab (*Scylla serrata*) haemolymph extract along with various volumes and control? Does the mantis shrimp (*Oratosquilla oratoria*) haemolymph extract exhibit more antimicrobial activity than the mud crab (*Scylla serrata*) against *Staphylococcus epidermidis* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*?

Table 2. Test for significant difference between mantis and mud crab across different concentration volumes

Bacteria	Extract	Volume	p-value	Significance	Ho Decision
<i>S. epidermidis</i>	Mantis shrimp vs. Mud crab	10	1.000	Not Significant	Accept
		20	0.869	Not Significant	Accept
		30	0.170	Not Significant	Accept
		40	0.635	Not Significant	Accept
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	Mantis shrimp vs. Mud crab	10	1.000	Not Significant	Accept
		20	1.000	Not Significant	Accept
		30	0.999	Not Significant	Accept
		40	1.000	Not Significant	Accept

It can be obtained from the Table 2 that there is no significant difference in the result findings on the zone of inhibition of the antimicrobial activity of mantis shrimp (*Oratosquilla oratoria*) and mud crab (*Scylla serrata*) along with its different volumes and control. The results may look different, but this difference is not statistically significant, thus the null hypothesis has been accepted.

It can also be shown as with the significant level of .05, the following p-values were not significant, therefore accepting the null hypothesis and also the mantis shrimp (*Oratosquilla oratoria*) exhibits antimicrobial activity the same as the mud crab (*Scylla serrata*). Still, the gold standard antibiotic produced a very efficient result against *Staphylococcus epidermidis* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

Conclusions

With the experimentation done and the data gathered, the researchers concluded that the mantis shrimp (*Oratosquilla oratoria*) and mud crab (*Scylla serrata*) extracts inhibit antimicrobial activity against *Staphylococcus epidermidis* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The antimicrobial activity of mantis shrimp and crab extracts show that as the volume of the concentration increases, the inhibition also increases. The antimicrobial effect against *Staphylococcus epidermidis* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* shows that the result of extracts in therapeutic effect is still not comparable to the gold standard used which was Gentamicin. The haemolymph of mantis shrimp has antimicrobial properties against the organisms *Staphylococcus epidermidis* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions made in the study, future studies should be made similar to the present investigation but different species to compare to the antimicrobial activity of mud crab (*Scylla serrata*). Future researchers may conduct research determining the antibacterial effect using another type of microorganism. Future researchers may conduct research using another antibiotic for positive and negative control in antimicrobial activity. Future researchers may conduct research determining the antifungal activity of mantis shrimp (*Oratosquilla oratoria*). Future researchers may use higher concentrations of the extracts of mantis shrimp (*Oratosquilla oratoria*) and mud crab (*Scylla serrata*).

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